

THE ESSENCE OF CORPORATE SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESPONSIBILITY FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This research is motivated by The condition that the implementation of the Corporate Social Responsibility program is one form of implementation of the concept of Good Corporate Governance. In Indonesia, related to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has been regulated in legislation, so that corporate social responsibility which was originally an area of ethical and moral responsibility of the company was then sharpened by positive law into a legal obligation. The characteristics of social and environmental responsibility which were originally voluntary have then changed into a legal obligation which is mandatory in nature. This research aims to This study addresses the issue of the nature of corporate social and environmental responsibility for sustainable development. This research is a normative legal study using philosophical, historical, statute, and conceptual approaches. The results of the study indicate that the essence of social and environmental responsibility by companies for sustainable development is the company's ongoing commitment to operate ethically and make a positive contribution to society and the environment, so that companies do not only focus on economic profits alone, but also consider the social and environmental impacts of all their operations, so that they can meet the needs of the present generation without sacrificing the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The suggestions that the author can provide from this research are: It is hoped that the government, both regional and central governments, will formulate derivative regulations or technical guidelines that regulate the implementation of CSR in more detail and operationally, including success indicators and reporting obligations to ensure that CSR is truly implemented as a sustainable commitment.

Keywords: Nature, Social Responsibility, Company, Sustainable Development.

INTRODUCTION

Companies are one of the effective sources and means of implementing national development policies. National development is a process of change towards better conditions through planned efforts with the primary goal of improving and enhancing the standard of living, welfare, and quality of life. (Rusli Razak, 2022) To achieve these development goals, the government consistently implements national development based on Pancasila, which encompasses all aspects of national life.

The government, as the holder of supreme authority, has the authority and obligation to direct and protect the community in carrying out its activities. Therefore, realizing national development must be carried out in synergy between the government and society, with the government acting as the regulator and the community as the primary actors in realizing national development to achieve a just and prosperous society. Justice and prosperity are the goals of national development, so the state must be present to protect and ensure the welfare of its people. (Nurhaedah, 2022)

Companies play a vital role in addressing welfare issues, as stipulated in the Investment Law, which requires companies to commit to participating in economic development to improve the quality of life and the environment through corporate social responsibility. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a form of corporate social and environmental responsibility, encompassing community-based service programs and activities. The goal of CSR is to improve community welfare and preserve the environment, particularly those surrounding the company's operational areas.

Corporate Social Responsibility is a company's contribution to sustainable development. A company's participation in sustainable development is by developing a program of corporate concern for the surrounding community, which is called corporate social responsibility. (Suparman, 2013) Corporate social responsibility is an implementation of moral awareness and is a voluntary act by the company to incur costs to make an important contribution to the continuity of the corporation itself, so that sustainable development goals can be achieved.

A contribution to the achievement of sustainable development goals that economically contributes to poverty eradication efforts and opens access to decent employment. Socially, it contributes to gender equality, good infrastructure innovation, building peaceful, inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities, settlements, and social life, as well as ensuring sustainable consumption patterns. Environmentally, it contributes to addressing the impacts of climate change, conserving and preserving natural resources, biodiversity, and environmentally friendly lifestyles.

Social responsibility and sustainable development become important when linked to environmental issues. The demand to implement social and environmental responsibilities becomes inevitable, when facts show that corporate consumption of natural resources reaches more than 30% of what is provided by nature/the environment. (Reza Rahman, 2009) Therefore, in using natural resources and in order to implement social and environmental responsibilities, companies need to be guided by the concept of sustainable development.

According to A. Sonny Keraf, the paradigm of sustainable development must be understood as the political ethics of development, namely a moral commitment about how development should be organized and implemented to achieve goals. (A. Sonny, 2010) The goals to be achieved in implementing sustainable development are a balance between economic growth, social welfare, and environmental sustainability. One way to achieve these goals is for companies to implement social and environmental responsibilities by creating programs that are always oriented towards sustainable development.

Through social and environmental responsibility programs that are oriented towards sustainable development, it is hoped that the ultimate goal of social and environmental responsibility will be achieved, namely positioning business entities to participate in realizing the concept of sustainable development, namely achieving a balance between economic growth, social welfare, and environmental sustainability.

The implementation of a corporate social responsibility program is one form of implementation of the concept of good corporate governance. Good corporate governance is necessary so that

business behavior has a reference point by regulating the relationship between all stakeholders that can be met proportionally, preventing significant errors in corporate strategy and ensuring that errors that occur can be corrected immediately. (Ashar, 2019)

In Indonesia, the philosophy related to corporate social responsibility can be seen in the 4th (fourth) paragraph of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia which states to "protect all the Indonesian people, all of Indonesia's homeland and to advance public welfare, educate the nation's life, and participate in implementing world order." Advancing public welfare is the responsibility of the state supported by companies in realizing the country's economic development. Because growth and a good economic climate are one of the things that support the growth and development of a company.

(Shandra, 2015) Corporate social responsibility is not only throwing away funds, because a company is not only to seek profit but must also contribute to the community and the environment around the company's establishment and running its business activities. Companies that are legal entities or sole proprietorships or those that are not legal entities are required to contribute to the community and the surrounding environment. There is no difference between sole proprietorships or non-legal entities and companies that are legal entities in corporate social responsibility.

Article 33 of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia is the basis for the Indonesian economic system. Based on the provisions of Article 33 paragraph (1) it states: "The economy is structured as a joint effort based on the principle of family". Article 33 paragraph (4), states: "The national economy is organized based on the principles of economic democracy with togetherness, fair efficiency, sustainability, environmental awareness, independence, and by maintaining a balance of progress and national economic unity". Article 33 is the constitutional basis of all laws and regulations regarding corporate social responsibility.

In Indonesia, corporate social responsibility has been regulated in legislation, so that corporate social responsibility, which was originally an area of ethical and moral responsibility for companies, has been sharpened by positive law into a legal obligation. The characteristics of social and environmental responsibility, which were originally voluntary, have then changed to a legal obligation that is mandatory. (Herdiansyah, et al., 2022) Based on the description of the background of the problem above, the problem in this study raises the question of what is the nature of corporate social and environmental responsibility for sustainable development?

RESEARCH METHODS

Based on the title and formulation of the problem above, this research is a normative legal research where the law is conceptualized as written in laws and regulations (law in books) or the law is conceptualized as a rule or norm that is a reference for human behavior that is considered appropriate. (Amiruddin & Asikin, 2004) In order to answer the problems in this research, the approaches used include the Philosophical Approach, Historical Approach, Statute Approach and Conceptual Approach. (Muhaimin, 2020) Types and Sources of Legal Materials in the form of Primary Legal Materials, Secondary Legal Materials and Tertiary

Legal Materials. The Legal Material Collection Technique in this research was obtained through Library Research. The legal materials collected and obtained in the research were analyzed through legal interpretation and then processed deductively, namely drawing conclusions from a general problem to the specific problem faced, then the analysis was carried out using qualitative methods, namely the legal materials presented in the form of a series of sentences that describe the results of the research based on the problem being studied regarding corporate social and environmental responsibility.

DISCUSSION

The Essence of Corporate Social and Environmental Responsibility for Sustainable Development

A company is any form of business that carries out any type of business that is permanent, continuous, and established, operates, and is domiciled within the territory of the Republic of Indonesia. (Muhammad, 2010) Every company is established with the aim of achieving maximum profit or gain. Therefore, in order to generate profit, the company always tries to find opportunities and chances to do something that can provide added value. If this cannot be controlled, it is possible that negative impacts can arise that can be detrimental to the environment and society. This can happen because, in general, companies still apply capitalist principles in carrying out their activities, namely achieving maximum profit with minimal costs by justifying any means. (Naning, 2017)

When examined, the existence of a company, in addition to incurring social costs, can also generate social benefits. Social benefits are the positive contributions or benefits a company's existence brings to society. A company's social benefits can be manifested in various physical and non-physical activities. Social benefits emerge as a manifestation of a company's social and environmental responsibility to its environment, also known as stakeholders.

Corporate social and environmental responsibility (CSR) is now familiar to the general public, as a company's response to the community environment. Corporate social and environmental responsibility relates to social responsibility, social welfare, and managing the community's quality of life. Industry and corporations, in this regard, play a role in promoting a healthy economy by considering environmental factors. Through corporate social and environmental responsibility, companies not only prioritize their goal of achieving maximum profit, but also encompass financial, social, and other environmental aspects.

Corporate social and environmental responsibility can be defined as a company's moral responsibility towards its stakeholders, particularly the communities surrounding its work and operations. Therefore, companies that implement social and environmental responsibility are viewed as moral agents, with the parameters of corporate success prioritizing moral and ethical principles that will benefit society.

Ethics and morals have different meanings. Although considered the same, they have different meanings and implications. Morals are often associated with individual actions, while ethics are often associated with the prevailing system.

Aristotle also explained ethics in the following point:

1. *Terminus tecbius*, The focus in this ethic is all human actions
2. *Manner and custom*, mDiscuss ethics related to procedures and customs (customs) inherent in human nature, which are related to the understanding of good and bad human behavior or actions. (A. Setiadarma, 2021)

Ethics builds bridges that unite the interests and expectations of every organization and culture. Thus, ethics contributes to building better mutual understanding and helps avoid conflict. Ethical corporate social and environmental responsibility governs relationships between organizations and stakeholders. It's important to remember that a company is not just a social, economic, and technological construct. It also emphasizes human resources. This means discussing social capital and the social dimensions related to the company's activities, which are reflected in its corporate social and environmental responsibility.

A company is closely connected to the business environment in which it operates. Broadly speaking, a company involves not only its direct stakeholders, such as employees and customers, but also local communities and ecological factors. Therefore, there is a strong connection between the company as a social construct and other types of companies that can also be seen as social constructs.

Thus, corporate social and environmental responsibility develops almost naturally and can be considered a moral responsibility that organizations assume in their relationships with their internal constituents and with their environment. (Valasquez, 2006)

Corporate social and environmental responsibility emerges as a company's moral obligation in its relationships with its partners. This collaboration will ensure the continuity of its operations and ultimately benefit the company. Social and environmental responsibility are activities that should contribute to the company, not weaken it. The fine line is very thin and must be managed with great care, as sometimes the best intentions can end in disaster. A lack of financial resources or misuse by a company hinders the development of necessary capital, requiring more investment and resulting in a rapid decline in profits.

Corporate involvement in social activities and ways of promoting social and environmental responsibility based on morality are elements that are attracting increasing attention from the mass media, business partners, and employees. That is why consumers and investors pay attention to the ethics embedded in corporate decisions and actions.

The moral and ethical principles of a company can be seen in the harmonious relationship between the company and the surrounding community, namely achieving the best results while minimizing losses for other community groups. This is to create a balance and equitable distribution of socio-economic welfare in society so that social jealousy no longer has the potential to become a source of conflict. As a general moral and ethical concept, the Company's social and environmental responsibility in practice must be channeled into concrete programs. One form of actualization is Community Development. Social and environmental responsibility is seen as a necessity to build a good and trustworthy image for the company.

The practice of sustainable corporate social and environmental responsibility as a Social Investment that results in the smooth operation of the Company. (Santoso, 2016) Thus, corporate social and environmental responsibility is understood as the embodiment of a commitment to corporate sustainability reflected in the triple bottom line "3P": profit, planet and people. In line with development, business companies must contribute to these three things. Basically, sustainability is a balance between economic, environmental and societal interests.

By implementing sustainable social and environmental responsibility programs, it is hoped that they will shape or create a more prosperous and independent community life. Each of these activities will involve a spirit of synergy from all parties, continuously building and creating prosperity, and ultimately, will create independence for the communities involved in the program. Social and environmental responsibility programs can only be sustainable if the programs created by a company truly represent a shared commitment from all elements within the company itself. (Lesmana, 2006)

The realization of corporate social responsibility must fulfill at least three forms, namely:

1. Realizing Good Corporate Governance

The term Good Corporate Governance (GCG) according to the Cadbury Committee of the United Kingdom is a set of regulations that regulate the relationship between shareholders, company management, creditors, government, employees, and other internal and external stakeholders related to their rights and obligations. Or in other words, a system that directs and controls the company. (Sukrisno, 2009) According to Agoes, Sukrisno defines good corporate governance as a system that regulates the relationship between the roles of the Board of Commissioners, the role of the Board of Directors, Shareholders and other Stakeholders. Good corporate governance/GCG is also mentioned as a transparent process for determining company goals, achieving and assessing their performance. (Sukrisno, 2009)

Good Corporate Governance, Good Corporate Governance arose due to several cases or scandals carried out by large companies both domestically and abroad as a result of the implementation of bad corporate management practices since being introduced by the OECD, the following principles of Good Corporate Governance have been used as a reference by countries in the world including Indonesia. These principles are formulated universally so that they can apply to all countries or companies and are aligned with the legal system, rules or values applicable in each country. The principles of good corporate governance include:

a. Accountability

This principle outlines the authority that the board of commissioners and directors must possess, along with their obligations to shareholders and other stakeholders. The board of directors is responsible for the successful management of the company in order to achieve the objectives set by the shareholders. Commissioners are responsible for the successful oversight and are required to provide advice to the board of directors regarding company management to achieve the company's objectives. Shareholders are responsible for the successful management of the company.

b. Responsibility

This principle requires companies, as well as their leaders and managers, to conduct their activities responsibly towards society and the environment, thereby maintaining long-term business continuity and gaining recognition as a Good Corporate Citizen. As company managers, we should avoid any transaction costs that could potentially harm third parties or other parties outside of the agreed-upon provisions, as implied by laws, regulations, contracts, and company business operational guidelines.

c. Transparency

To maintain objectivity in conducting business, this principle requires companies to disclose material and relevant information in a timely and accurate manner, easily accessible and understandable to stakeholders. This information includes information about the company's financial condition, financial performance, ownership, and management. This information is audited independently. Disclosure is essential to ensure shareholders and others are aware of the company's condition and can enhance the value of their shares.

d. Fairness

All stakeholders must have the opportunity to receive fair treatment from the company. Enforcing this principle within the company will prohibit reprehensible practices by insiders that harm others. Every member of the board of directors must be transparent if they discover transactions containing a conflict of interest.

The purpose of implementing good corporate governance (GCG) is not only to assess the company's performance but also to create added value for all stakeholders, prevent and reduce manipulation and significant errors in managing the organization and increase efforts so that stakeholders are not harmed. According to Tjager et al., one of the benefits of implementing good corporate governance is that theoretically GCG practices can increase the company's value (Value Added). Recently, there has been a growing public demand for transparency and corporate accountability as a form of good corporate governance (GCG). One implementation of GCG in companies is through the implementation of corporate social responsibility (CSR), which in Indonesian means the company's social and environmental responsibility. In the era of globalization, awareness of the implementation of corporate social responsibility has become crucial along with the increasing public concern for environmentally friendly products or goods.

Corporate social responsibility Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a company's commitment to ethical behavior and contributing to sustainable economic development. Another commitment is to improve the quality of life for employees and their families, local communities, and the wider community. Harmony between the company and its surrounding community can be achieved if top management fully commits to implementing CSR as a form of public accountability. One of the principles of good corporate governance is accountability, namely the conformity of company management to applicable laws and sound corporate principles. Recently, there have been three public interests that companies tend to ignore. First,

companies are only responsible to shareholders, while the communities around the company's domicile are less concerned. Second, the negative impacts caused by corporate activities are increasing and must be borne by the surrounding community, while the majority of benefits are enjoyed only by the company's shareholders. Third, most of the victims of the community have difficulty claiming compensation from the company concerned. The emergence of issues of global warming, ozone layer depletion, forest destruction, damage to locations around mining areas, water pollution due to toxic waste, environmental pollution from oil drilling, air pollution due to indiscriminate forest burning, seawater pollution due to oil spills from leaking oil tankers, and so on are negative consequences of the emergence of business activities that are solely oriented towards profit without regard for the negative impacts that harm society and the earth we live on. The concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR), stakeholder analysis, and the like are responses to company actions or business activities that have harmed society and the earth we live on. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a company's responsibility to company owners/shareholders and employees, which is manifested in achieving profitability and company growth levels and the company's responsibility to improve the welfare and competence of the community, create jobs, and preserve the environment for future generations.

2. Participate in sustainable development

According to the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), sustainable development means development with a long-term perspective, encompassing intergenerational development and striving to provide sufficient resources and a healthy environment, so that it can support life.

3. Maintain relationships with the community.

Relationship-building efforts are carried out throughout all phases of the project. The goal, in addition to fostering good relations, is to accommodate local residents' complaints and concerns so that negative impacts can be mitigated. Sustainable development is development that aims to meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. To achieve this goal, four principles must be met:

1. Fulfillment of Human Needs.
2. Maintaining ecological integrity (Maintenance of Ecological Integrity);
3. Social Equity;
4. Opportunity to determine one's own destiny (Self Determination).

The sustainable development paradigm has three main pillars, namely Economic Growth, Poverty Alleviation and Sustainability which are based on two important ideas, namely:

1. The idea of needs, especially the essential needs of the world's poor, must be given top priority.
2. The idea of limitations that stem from the state of technology and social organization of society regarding the environment's ability to meet current and future needs.

Development policies are directed towards achieving prosperity and well-being for all its people. The main problems faced in achieving social welfare are unemployment, unequal income distribution, and poverty. These problems are interrelated and cannot be solved separately. (Suhaimi, 2016) According to Yacob et al., sustainable development must fulfill at least four components as follows: 1) Fulfillment of basic needs, such as; Material needs and non-material needs; 2) Environmental maintenance, such as; carrying out conservation and reducing consumption; 3) Social justice, such as: Future justice and present justice. And 4) Opportunity for self-determination, such as: independent communities and participatory democracy. The principles of sustainable development can be realized if supported by good governance. Good governance is categorized as good if public resources and problems are managed effectively and efficiently in response to the needs of the community. Good governance as formulated by ICEL requires five things, namely: Representative institutions capable of carrying out the function of control and channeling public aspirations (Effective Representative System); Independent, clean and professional courts (Judicial Independence); Bureaucracy that is responsive to the needs of the community and has integrity (Reliable and Responsive Bureaucracy); Civil society that is capable of carrying out the control function (Strong and participatory Civil Society); and decentralization and strong representative institutions (Democratic decentralization). (Suhaimi, 2016)

The government's commitment to building and realizing Good Governance by implementing the principles of Transparency, Accountability, Efficiency, Effectiveness, and participation, has begun since 1999, marked by the birth of the Law on Regional Government. This Law on Regional Government has been revised several times, most recently by Law Number 23 of 2014. The birth of the Law on Regional Government, marks a shift and change in the Paradigm of government from a centralized government to a decentralized government. The government delegates some of its authority to regional governments to regulate and manage their own households.

Good, democratic governance, namely in the implementation of the duties, functions, and responsibilities of the government, can create a just, prosperous, and prosperous society. To that end, the government implements National Development as a practice of Pancasila to develop the whole Indonesian people and the entire Indonesian society. National development expects that no one is left behind and not reached by development activities. Recognizing that the government has limited resources, both in terms of funds, manpower, and skills, a Synergy strategy is used known as the three pillars: Government, Business World, and Society. National development is not only the responsibility of the government and the business world alone, but the entire community has a role to play in realizing social welfare and improving the quality of life of the community. Today, the business world is no longer only concerned with company financial records (single bottom line), but also includes financial, social, and environmental aspects (Triple bottom line). Of these three pillars, the business world is believed to have a significant role and contribution to the success of national development. Companies are very important for the government, because companies, no matter how small, are part of the economic force that produces goods and services to meet the needs of society.

Looking at the description above, we can draw the conclusion that the essence of social and environmental responsibility by companies for sustainable development is the company's ongoing commitment to operate ethically and make a positive contribution to society and the environment by enabling companies to allocate resources, expertise, and innovation to achieve prosperity goals fairly and equitably, so that companies do not only focus on economic profits alone, but also consider the social and environmental impacts of all their operations, so that they can meet the needs of the present generation without sacrificing the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Thus, corporate social and environmental responsibility is not just a momentary philanthropic activity, but a long-term commitment to operate ethically and responsibly, covering everything from sustainable business practices to the social and environmental impacts of company operations, so as to improve the quality of life for employees, local communities, and society at large, and ensure that companies do not only pursue financial profits, but also consider the social and environmental impacts of their activities. This is in line with the principle of sustainable development which emphasizes the balance between economic, social, and environmental needs. Based on the author's explanation, social and environmental responsibility essentially exists because of the inherent interests within them. The existence or emergence of social and environmental responsibility is motivated by the presence of these interests. Therefore, its implementation is an effort to fulfill these interests. Fulfillment of these interests must be carried out in a balanced manner to avoid conflicts.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusions

The essence of corporate social and environmental responsibility for sustainable development is the company's ongoing commitment to operate ethically and make a positive contribution to society and the environment by enabling the company to allocate resources, expertise, and innovation to achieve prosperity goals fairly and equitably, so the company does not only focus on economic profits alone, but also considers the social and environmental impacts of all its operations, so that it can meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Therefore, corporate social and environmental responsibility is not just a momentary philanthropic activity, but a long-term commitment to operate ethically and responsibly that includes everything from sustainable business practices to the social and environmental impacts of the company's operations, so that it can improve the quality of life for employees, local communities, and society at large as a whole. , and ensures that companies do not only pursue financial profits, but also consider the social and environmental impacts of their activities. This is in line with the principles of sustainable development which emphasize the balance between economic, social, and environmental needs.

2. Suggestions

It is hoped that governments, both regional and central, will formulate derivative regulations or technical guidelines that govern CSR implementation in greater detail and operationally,

including success indicators and reporting obligations. This is crucial to ensure that CSR is truly implemented as a sustainable commitment. Furthermore, companies are encouraged to integrate sustainable development principles throughout their operational chains, not limited to formal CSR activities. This includes environmentally friendly production practices, waste management, energy efficiency, and fair and inclusive labor practices.

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